

A Dual Linear-polarized Gap Waveguide Antenna Element for Radar and Communications at 77 GHz

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Abstract—A novel two-port antenna employing Gap Waveguide technology introduces $\pm 45^\circ$ slant polarizations for Joint Communication and Sensing (JCAS) systems or polarimetric radars in the 76 – 81 GHz frequency band. The subarray antenna comprises a two-layer radiating structure: the lower part features vertical slots radiating horizontal polarization, while the upper part integrates a septum polarizer and side metallic ridges. The septum polarizer converts horizontal to circular polarization by creating orthogonal electric field components with a 90° phase difference, while side ridges compensate for this phase difference, generating slant-polarized waves. This method achieves slant polarization by exciting the antenna ports without needing cavities to alter electric field orientation. The antenna, with two elements, attains a peak gain of 8.97 dBi within the 76 – 81 GHz frequency band, demonstrating an axial ratio exceeding 30 dB at $\pm 45^\circ$ slant polarization.

Index Terms—Joint Communications and Sensing, Gap Waveguide Technology, Isolation, Slant polarization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Full-duplex (FD) systems are wireless systems that simultaneously apply the same frequency band for transmitting/receiving signals for communications or Joint Communication and Sensing (JCAS) systems, enabling bi-directional communications. FD systems can significantly improve wireless systems' capacity by efficiently using the available spectrum, consequently providing higher data rates [1]. Due to simultaneous transmission and reception, FD is currently being considered for emerging joint communication and sensing systems [2]. A major challenge for FD systems is self-interference (SI) between communication and beamforming signals. And SI cancellation (SIC) is crucial for a reliable FD system. In the literature, different SIC techniques have been proposed to achieve desired isolation in FD systems, such as beamforming techniques, antenna/polarization diversity techniques, etc. (see, e.g., [3], [4]). In the case of polarization diversity, recently, dual circular polarized (CP) array antennas have been widely used in wireless communication systems and radars to reduce self-interference and to decrease correlation between the beamforming fields [5], [6]. However, two orthogonal electric field components of right/left-handed circular polarization can interfere with each other because the polarization of a reflected wave may change after bouncing from a scattering object, offering lower cross-polarization isolation. Hence, circular polarization may not be a proper candidate to eliminate the SI.

In addition, as well-known, the inter-element spacing of $\lambda/2$ is not satisfied by certain antenna elements depending on their dimensions, leading to unwanted grating lobes. On the other hand, orthogonal linear polarized antennas are an appropriate choice to use in multibeam radars and communication systems [7]. In [8], an all-metal phased array with polarization reconfigurability was introduced, and arbitrary linear polarizations were produced from the orthogonal circularly polarized waves generated by the septum polarizer. However, the array antenna has a complex design because of the use of feeding coaxial cables. In [9], a gap waveguide-based 45° slant-polarized phased array antenna was proposed and experimentally verified. The proposed array antenna has three radiating layers that convert horizontal polarization through an in-between cavity to slant polarization. As a result, a -45° polarization can be obtained by mirroring the slots relative to the yz plane, and, in the case of shared aperture arrays, coupling between the elements is introduced by the asymmetric structure.

In this paper, we propose a novel antenna structure to achieve $\pm 45^\circ$ slant polarizations, which can be used for either communication or sensing, or either as the transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx) parts of a communication system or as the Tx and Rx parts of a radar system. The new proposed antenna offers a fully symmetric structure by exciting two corresponding ports of the antenna to produce dual linear polarization and avoids using in-between cavities (seen in [9]), which make the structure asymmetric. In addition, the antenna structure will significantly control the inter-element coupling in the shared aperture arrays since the inter-element space is constant. The septum polarizer and side ridges have been employed on the radiating layer of the antenna to convert the horizontal polarization to orthogonal slant polarization.

II. DESIGN OF THE PROPOSED ANTENNA

This section describes the design process of the two-port slant-polarized antenna. The proposed antenna is simulated and optimized with the CST Microwave Studio simulation software. The antenna structure consists of a distribution layer and a combined radiating layer illustrated in Fig. 1. As shown in Fig. 1, the distribution layer guides electromagnetic waves through two ridges between the metallic pins towards two pairs of vertical slots. Two rows with two vertical slots are on the bottom of the radiating layer. The inter-element spacing of

the right/left aligned vertical slots is chosen equal to $\lambda_g/2$ for in-phase exciting the slots and avoiding grating lobes. The septum polarizer generates the two orthogonal right and left-handed circularly-polarized modes with even and odd modes exciting conditions [10]. For a better understanding of the mode analysis of the structure, a graphical visualization is shown in Fig. 2. The excitation at each slot can be decomposed into an even and odd mode, and the antenna output due to slot 1 or slot 2 is the summation of even and odd modes. As shown in Fig. 2, when slot 1 is excited, the polarization of the propagating electromagnetic wave on the aperture of the antenna is LHCP. Similarly, when slot 2 is excited, the polarization of the propagating electromagnetic wave on the aperture of the antenna is RHCP. The stepped septum polarizer can be ideally matched and create two orthogonal components with the same amplitude and 90° phase difference to achieve CP polarizations at the antenna aperture. To generate the CP wave, the following conditions must be satisfied by the electric field in the septum

$$|E_D| = |E_y| - |E_x| = 0 \text{ dB} \quad (1)$$

$$\angle E_D = \angle E_y - \angle E_x = \pm 90^\circ, \quad (2)$$

where amplitudes and phases of the TE_{01} mode in the septum polarizer along the y -direction and the TE_{10} mode along the x -direction on the radiation aperture should satisfy the above-mentioned conditions. The terms $|E_D|$ and $\angle E_D$ are the amplitude and phase differences at the radiation aperture of the septum polarizer and $(|E_y|, |E_x|)$ and $(\angle E_y, \angle E_x)$ refer to the amplitude and phase of orthogonal electric fields produced by the septum polarizer, respectively.

Hence, it is straightforward to see that the amplitude and phase responses will be altered when the size of the antenna aperture changes, consequently affecting the polarization of radiated waves. For this purpose, metallic ridges have been deployed on the opposite sides of each aperture to change the effective aperture size [8]. The change of aperture size is directly linked to the phase condition. The phase difference condition (2) at the radiation aperture are given by [11]

$$\angle E_D = (\beta_y - \beta_x)h, \quad (3)$$

where β_y and β_x are the phase constants of the TE_{01} and TE_{10} modes, and h is the height of radiation cavity of the antenna including the septum polarizer and metallic ridges. The parameter h has been optimized and fixed during the achieving circular polarization, so to change the phase condition, we need to change the value of the term $(\beta_y - \beta_x)$. As we know, the phase constant in the guided-wave structure can be expressed by [11]

$$\beta = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{\lambda}{\lambda_c}\right)^2}, \quad (4)$$

where λ is the free-space wavelength, and λ_c is the cut-off wavelength, and β can be controlled by altering λ_c . This can be realized by loading the metallic ridges to the aperture of the antenna structure. Due to the antenna configuration,

Fig. 1. Perspective view of the antenna.

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of the septum polarizer showing the input ports associated with slot 1 and slot 2, as well as the common physical port at the device output.

Fig. 3. Radiation aperture demonstration for polarization conversion.

changing β_y further is difficult. On the other hand, there is enough freedom to add the ridges along the x -direction to change β_x . The cut-off frequency will change by changing the metallic ridges dimension; therefore, its cut-off wavelength and β_x of the TE_{10} mode will change. It is worthwhile to note that by optimizing the dimensions, the ridges perturb the E -field distribution of the TE_{10} mode, compensating for the amplitude difference $|E_D|$ caused by the presence of the ridges. By keeping the amplitude condition (1) constant and canceling out the 90° phase difference (created by the septum polarizer) by metallic ridges, $\pm 45^\circ$ polarizations can be successfully created as schematically shown in Fig. 3.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, the simulated results for the designed antenna are presented. Fig. 4 shows the return loss and axial

Fig. 4. Simulated S-parameter results and Axial Ratio (AR).

Fig. 5. Co-polarized and X-polarized simulated patterns of the antenna at frequencies 77, 78, and 79 GHz (a) E-plane and (b) H-plane.

ratio results. An impedance bandwidth defined at S_{11} , and S_{22} less than 10 dB is obtained over the target 76 – 81 GHz frequency band. A good impedance matching between the different parts of the antenna has been achieved. Also shown in Fig. 4, the axial ratio demonstrates that the antenna produces fairly good linearly polarized waves within the frequency band from 76 – 79.5 GHz, i.e., with an $AR \geq 30$ dB.

The simulated E-plane ($\phi = 45^\circ$) and H-plane ($\phi = -45^\circ$) radiation patterns are shown in Fig. 5 for the Co- and X-Pol components (i.e., co- and cross-polarized components, respectively) at three frequencies. The Co- and X-pol results show that the $\pm 45^\circ$ polarizations have been nicely produced.

The electric field distribution on the antenna aperture shown in Fig. 6 illustrates the resulting slant polarization due to the excitation of slot 1 producing the $+45^\circ$ polarization, while exciting slot 2 produces the -45° polarization.

IV. BEAM CORRELATION CHARACTERIZATION

In this section, we characterize the beam correlation produced by the two orthogonally polarized elements by [12]

$$\rho_{12,BC} = \frac{|\oint \mathbf{F}_1 \cdot \mathbf{F}_2^* d\Omega|^2}{\oint |\mathbf{F}_1|^2 d\Omega \oint |\mathbf{F}_2|^2 d\Omega}, \quad (5)$$

where $\rho_{12,BC}$ is the correlation coefficient, \mathbf{F}_1 is the beam produced by the antenna when slot 1 is excited, and \mathbf{F}_2 is the beam produced by the antenna when slot 2 is excited

Fig. 6. Electric field distribution on the antenna aperture (a) when slot 1 is excited and (b) when slot 2 is excited.

Fig. 7. Beam correlation between the two beams produced by exciting the two ports of the antenna.

and the symbol $*$ denotes the complex conjugate operation. The symbol \cdot denotes the scalar product of two vectorial magnitudes.

If the two beams are ideally orthogonal, then $\rho_{12,BC} = 0$, while if the beams are non-orthogonal then $\rho_{12,BC} = 1$. In all the other cases, the result will be greater than 0, but less than 1. Hence, we aim to produce orthogonal beams; therefore, the best performance will be for $\rho_{12,BC}$ close to 0. In practical applications, achieving fully uncorrelated beams is difficult. Thus, $\rho_{12,BC} < 0.5$ is commonly considered good in practical applications [13]. The correlation between the two beams at different frequencies is calculated using (5) and has been demonstrated in Fig. 7. The best beam non-orthogonality, regardless of S-parameter results, is achieved at 78 GHz. The results show that two beams are sufficiently uncorrelated in the operating frequency band, assuming they operate in an isotropic multipath fading environment.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a new method to design a two-port antenna based on the gap waveguide technology capable of producing orthogonal slant polarization. The whole structure is comprised of two layers containing a distribution layer that guides the electromagnetic fields through a ridge, a combined radiating layer including a bottom part to configure the vertical polarization, and the top part comprising the septum polarizer and ridges to convert the horizontal polarization to

slant polarization. The proposed antenna produces dual slant polarizations by exciting the two corresponding ports, which makes the antenna symmetric and a proper choice for use in shared aperture arrays. The beam correlation coefficient has been calculated to assess the antenna performance. Given the presented simulation and numerical results, the proposed antenna is a good candidate for joint communication and sensing (JCAS) systems, which use orthogonal polarizations for each part to enhance isolation due to self-interference.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The H2020-MSCA Project 955629 ITN-5VC has funded this work. Funding from the ELLIIT strategic research environment (<https://elliit.se/>) is also appreciated.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Liu, F. R. Yu, H. Ji, V. C. M. Leung and X. Li, "In-Band Full-Duplex Relaying: A Survey, Research Issues and Challenges," in *IEEE Communications Surveys and Tutorials*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 500-524, Secondquarter 2015, doi: 10.1109/COMST.2015.2394324.
- [2] M. A. Islam, G. C. Alexandropoulos and B. Smida, "Integrated Sensing and Communication with Millimeter Wave Full Duplex Hybrid Beamforming," *ICC 2022 - IEEE International Conference on Communications*, Seoul, Korea, Republic of, 2022, pp. 4673-4678, doi: 10.1109/ICC45855.2022.9838368.
- [3] G. C. Alexandropoulos, M. A. Islam and B. Smida, "Full Duplex Hybrid A/D Beamforming with Reduced Complexity Multi-Tap Analog Cancellation," *2020 IEEE 21st International Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications (SPAWC)*, Atlanta, GA, USA, 2020, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/SPAWC48557.2020.9154241.
- [4] C. K. Sheemar and D. Stock, "Hybrid Beamforming and Combining for Millimeter Wave Full Duplex Massive MIMO Interference Channel," *2021 IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM)*, Madrid, Spain, 2021, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/GLOBECOM46510.2021.9685302.
- [5] M. Ferrando-Rocher, J. I. Herranz-Herruzo, A. Valero-Nogueira and B. Bernardo-Clemente, "Switchable T-Slot for Dual-Circularly-polarized Slot-Array Antennas in Ka-Band," in *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 20, no. 10, pp. 1953-1957, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2021.3101156.
- [6] Z. Zang, A. U. Zaman, J. Yang, C. Bencivenni and K. Konstantinidis, "Single Layer Dual Circularly polarized Antenna Elements for Automotive Radar at 77 GHz," *2021 15th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP)*, Dusseldorf, Germany, 2021, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.23919/EuCAP51087.2021.9411028.
- [7] Y. Cao, G. A. E. Vandenbosch and S. Yan, "Low-Profile Dual-polarized Multi-Beam Antenna Based on Pillbox Reflector and 3D-Printed Ridged Waveguide," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 70, no. 9, pp. 7578-7591, Sept. 2022, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2022.3171728.
- [8] L. Sun et al., "All-Metal Phased Array With Full polarization Reconfigurability," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 71, no. 4, pp. 3349-3360, April 2023, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2023.3244004.
- [9] A. Bagheri et al., "A 16×16 45° Slant-polarized Gapwaveguide Phased Array With 65-dBm EIRP at 28 GHz," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 71, no. 2, pp. 1319-1329, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2022.3227718.
- [10] X. Cheng, Y. Wang, Y. Yao, T. Yu, J. Yu and X. Chen, "Compact W-Band Septum Orthomode Transducer Based on Gap Waveguide," in *IEEE Microwave and Wireless Technology Letters*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 133-136, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1109/LMWC.2022.3211859.
- [11] Y. -M. Yang, C. -W. Yuan and B. -L. Qian, "A Novel Phase Shifter for Ku-Band High-Power Microwave Applications," in *IEEE Transactions on Plasma Science*, vol. 42, no. 1, pp. 51-54, Jan. 2014, doi: 10.1109/TPS.2013.2288946.
- [12] R. G. Zarnagh and A. Alayón Glazunov, "Correlation and Non-Orthogonality Figures of Merit of Beamforming Fields," *2023 17th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP)*, Florence, Italy, 2023, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.23919/EuCAP57121.2023.10133475.
- [13] A. Iqbal, M. Al-Hasan, I. B. Mabrouk and T. A. Denidni, "Capsule Endoscopic MIMO Antenna With Radiation Pattern and Polarization Diversity," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 71, no. 4, pp. 3146-3154, April 2023, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2023.3244035.